

**FORMATION OF DISCOURSE COMPETENCE IN THE SPHERE OF ORAL
COMMUNICATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS****Abdurasulova Nilufar Abdusalim qizi**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7039842>

Annotation. The spot of rambling ability in the design of open not set in stone by summing up the consequences of the examination of logical and strategic writing. The meaning of the ideas of “discourse” and “discursive competence” is given. The oddity of the review lies in the way that it presents the part organization of the substance of desultory skill, which is framed while showing a foreign language through an instructive gathering. The primary attributes of the instructive discussion are depicted. The outcomes can be applied while involving electronic courses in the instructive cycle.

Keywords: communicative competence, discursive competence, discourse, learning strategies, foreign language teaching process.

Introduction. The social request of the advanced data and multicultural society expects that higher instructive foundations give the production of ideal circumstances for helping understudies foreign language correspondence to tackle the issues of intercultural connection at the world level. The capacity to convey turns into an essential part in the readiness of exceptionally qualified trained professionals. The need to work on the nature of language preparing in higher expert training is critical. The cutting edge model of schooling structures an elevated degree of expert skill among understudies, one of the parts of which is communicative competence. The capacity to complete viable discourse connection in a foreign language is remembered for the substance of foreign language communicative competence, which permits college graduates to convey unreservedly in a multilingual climate. Open skill is the premise of professional schooling with regards to strengths whose principal movement is correspondence in the expert field. As of late, studies have gave the idea that are committed to the thought of individual parts of informative ability. Be that as it may, not all parts get equivalent consideration. Because of the developing interest of scholars and professionals in different parts of intercultural correspondence, the majority of examination is pointed toward settling issues connected with the social and social boundaries of correspondence. A critical number of works are dedicated to the issues of socio-social skill (Baranova N.A.). In this article, we will decide the spot of verbose capability as a feature of open skill by checking on the logical and strategic writing on this subject.[]

The motivation behind our review is to decide the substance of rambling skill, shaped while showing a foreign language to understudies of a language college through an instructive discussion. In the science and practice of showing foreign languages, insufficient consideration is paid to the idea of “discourse”, which is critical for the arrangement of digressive skill. The greater part of the current investigations are given to the phonetic part of the issue of talks or talk examination: “Design and semantics of factious discourse” E.N. Belova; “Melodious competence as an object of linguo-tasteful understanding” A.V. Flory and others. There are numerous meanings of the idea of “discourse” in the logical writing. At various times, different researchers offered their understandings of this idea (T.A. van Dyck, P. Serio, N.D. Arutyunova, V.I. Karasik, A.A. Kibrik, E.S. Kubryakova, Yu.S. Stepanov, G. G. Slyshkin, V. E. Chernyavskaya and others). Be that as it may, as a general rule, they don't go against one another, however supplement and give a more complete depiction of this idea according to the perspective of various sciences. T.A. van Dijk is one of the originators behind the hypothesis of talk.

The researcher proposed a meaning of talk, which started to be effectively utilized in mainstream researchers and filled in as the reason for additional point by point meanings of this term and the making of groupings of the fundamental qualities of talk. The worth of the definition proposed by T.A. van Dijk, is to recognize the “informative occasion” as a perplexing solidarity of semantic structure, importance and activity. It is proposed to consider talk from the stance of a practical methodology as an open occasion that happens between the speaker and audience (eyewitness, and so forth) during the time spent informative activity in a specific worldly, spatial and different settings. We likewise note that talk as an open occasion can be discourse (composed or oral) and have verbal and non-verbal parts. Following the regulation of talk proposed by T.A. van Dyck, A.A. Kibrik makes a capability of the framework qualities of talk, as for which coming up next is shown while portraying talk: class; register (gaming, business or institutional); type or channel of data transmission (oral, composed, mental, gestural and electronic submodus); useful style; convention. Concerning the desultory capability of understudies of a language college, here we characterize it as a bunch of information and abilities that understudies who concentrate on a foreign language should have to intelligently offer viewpoints, making a syntactically and lexically right text, sufficient to the open circumstance, as well with respect to the right translation of the text. Without a doubt, the idea of “discourse” isn't the toward the end in significance in the

meaning of digressive capability. This is because of the new change in perspectives towards “discourse” and “text”. Already, these two terms in the etymological writing were same and were utilized in equal. Right now, language specialists recognize these two ideas and characterize the text as a result of discourse movement, communicated in oral or composed structure, which is necessary and reasonable. Talk is seen as a complex open peculiarity, as “the entirety of everything spoken and figured out in a specific explicit circumstance in some period of the existence of a given gathering”, or, as a text drenched throughout everyday life, as per the meaning of N.D. Aratyunova.

One of the key information that understudies of a foreign language ought to have is information about the kinds and classes of talk. IN AND. Karasik characterizes the accompanying classifications of talk: 1) members in correspondence (a class that incorporates status-job and situational-open qualities); 2) states of correspondence (a classification that decides the extent of correspondence, the informative climate); 3) association of correspondence (a classification that decides the thought processes, objectives and methodologies of correspondence, control of correspondence and changeability of correspondence implies); 4) methods of correspondence (a classification that characterizes style and kind). V.I. Karasik likewise characterizes two kinds of talk - individual situated and status-arranged. The main exists as ordinary (regular) and existential (philosophical and imaginative discourse) correspondence, and the second - as pretending correspondence as per the areas of movement, for instance, mass data, political, business, logical, instructive, military, sports, strict , legitimate and different sorts of status-arranged competence.

The more strategic arrangements, the more successful the quest for better approaches for learning. As of late, the open direction in showing a foreign language has been strengthening, which brings about various cardinal changes in the objectives and content of showing a foreign language. It is vital not exclusively to know the language, yet to have the option to utilize it sufficiently in genuine open circumstances. In this manner, there is a need to create “rambling skill”. Prior to discussing rambling capability, one ought to initially investigate the essential ideas that are straightforwardly connected with this term. Most importantly, it is important to recognize the ideas of “capability” and skill and consider informative ability as an essential design, which incorporates digressive skill. The main in this work is the idea of talk, its temperament and design. Talking about ability, it is important that researchers frequently liken this term with capability. I.A. Zimnyaya distinguishes two choices for the

relationship of these ideas, researchers either separate them or on the other hand recognize them, which happens significantly more frequently. How about we follow the fundamental achievements in the development of the idea of “communicative ability” from the snapshot of its introduction to the current day.[]

All along of the improvement of the idea of “communicative competence”, there has been a logical inconsistency between the allies of a limited and expansive comprehension of the information and abilities important to convey in a foreign language. In the logical world, there has forever been a differentiation among information and its execution, so the actual idea of “skill” can't be called new. The expression “skill” was first presented by the American etymologist N. Chomsky in 1965 corresponding to information on the language framework, etymological signs, lexical and syntactic structures, and not according to the utilization of this information in circumstances of genuine correspondence. If N. Chomsky, who proposed during the 1960s. of the last 100 years, the idea of “phonetic skill”, considered the psychological (“knowledge”) model of language ability as all inclusive principles to be fundamental and adequate for correspondence, then as of now at that period D. Hymes and S. Savignon guarded the possibility of not phonetic, yet open skill.

Before long, the idea of “open capacity” additionally showed up - capacity/limit, which was expounded on by L. Bachman, S. Savignon, H. Widdowson. N. Chomsky proceeded with the thoughts of language structure created by F. de Saussure. Progressively, the strategic term “communicative competence” showed up in the homegrown and unfamiliar procedure rather than the “lexical ability” of N. Chomsky. Another American language specialist, D. Hymes, contended that for an undeniable correspondence (informative demonstration) having just information about the language framework, lexical and syntactic rules isn't sufficient. In the homegrown study of language, the expression “communicative competence” was brought into logical use by M.N. Vyatyutnev. He proposed to figure out communicative competence “as the decision and execution of projects of discourse conduct contingent upon the capacity of an individual to explore in a specific climate of correspondence; the capacity to characterize circumstances relying upon the subject, undertakings, open mentalities, abilities that emerge in understudies before the discussion, as well as during the discussion during the time spent common variation”.

Conclusion. Subsequently, we can presume that the learning discussion fills in as an instructive setting for the development of rambling unknown dialect

capability, which predetermines the information and comprehension of the framework qualities of talk by understudies and the capacity to apply them in suitable circumstances of correspondence as a method for executing discourse expectations. The development of digressive skill through a mastering gathering should be viewed as in close association with the rise of the need furthermore, thought process in the articulation. Such procedures ought to be utilized that improve the discourse of understudies with new discourse adages, structure relational abilities, specifically comparable to various composing designs, and foster the capacity of understudies to remove data from the text. As to the states of the discussion, to be specific correspondence in a virtual climate, the capacity to sensibly fabricate an assertion obtains extraordinary significance, which is really the substance of desultory capability.

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